

CHORAL DATA 'TRUST' EXPERIMENT WHITE PAPER

*Prototyping a GLAM Trusted Data Intermediary
for Public Interest AI*

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Acknowledgements

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The *Choral Data 'Trust' Experiment* would not be possible without the following UK choirs:

Blackburn People's Choir, Blackburn
Carnoustie Choir, Carnoustie
Cunninghame Choir, Beith
The Fitzhardinge Consort, Bristol
The Fourth Choir, London
HIVE Choir, Belfast
Leeds Vocal Movement, Leeds
London Contemporary Voices, London
Musarc, London
New London Chamber Choir, London
Open Arts Community Choir, Belfast
Ordsall Acappella Singers, Salford
The Ravenswood Singers, Newcastle
South Lakes A Cappella, Windermere
Spectrum Singers, Penarth

We thank our research advisors **Sylvie Delacroix** (Centre for Data Futures, King's College London) and **Matt Prewitt** (RadicalxChange), as well as our legal advisors **Alex Lawrence-Archer** and **Ravi Naik** (AWO) and **Alasdair Taylor** (Keystone Law).

We also thank the following colleagues sharing their feedback and insight on this paper:

Aleksandra Berditchevskaia,
Centre for Collective Intelligence
Design, Nesta
Tim Davies, Connected by Data
Flynn Devine, Boundary Object Studio
Tommie Introna, Serpentine Arts
Technologies
Brandon Jackson, Public AI Network
Joe Massey, Open Data Institute
Kasia Odrozek, Mozilla Foundation
Reema Patel, Elgon Social Research
& ESRC Digital Good Network
Aidan Peppin, Cohere
Emily Rempel, Civic Data Cooperative
& University of Liverpool
Reema Selhi, DACS
Alek Tarkowski, Open Future Foundation
Janis Wong, The Law Society
of England and Wales

Ivanova, V. and Ding, J. (2025). "Choral Data 'Trust' Experiment White Paper".
<https://futureartecosystems.org/project/choral-data-trust-experiment/whitepaper>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14859320

Executive Summary

The rapid advancement of generative artificial intelligence (AI) has intensified debates around who controls and benefits from the data used to build AI systems and how it is obtained. In response, visions for building public interest AI ecosystems are emerging, which aim to promote data and AI as public goods and enable diverse voices to shape AI development. This paper presents findings from the **Choral Data ‘Trust’ Experiment**, a pioneering initiative by Serpentine, a UK public art institution, to test new approaches to governing AI training data through a real-world case study with 15 UK choirs.

The experiment centered on choral recordings contributed by over 300 choristers for an AI art exhibition titled *The Call* ↗. Through the appointment of a data steward, months of choir engagement, and exploration of governance frameworks with a team of legal advisors, the project developed and tested concrete mechanisms for more participatory approaches to dataset governance. This work is particularly timely as the UK government conducts consultations on AI and copyright policy.

Three key insights have emerged from the experiment. First, it demonstrated the need for data governance approaches that go beyond individual opt-in/opt-out, highlighting the impact of building capacity for meaningful participation through relationship-building and structured preference-gathering towards outcomes such as trust and transparency. Second, it established legal frameworks that enable creative communities to collectively exercise and negotiate their rights, while also revealing limitations in current individual rights-based approaches. Third, it validated the potential for cultural institutions to serve as trusted intermediaries in AI development, though this role requires dedicated resources and expertise.

The findings suggest several important implications for policy and practice. There is a clear need for investment in data stewardship infrastructure and public digital literacy resources to enable meaningful public participation in AI governance. Legal frameworks must be clarified and strengthened to better support collective data rights. Cultural institutions require support to play new roles in AI development, alongside policies that enable public interest AI to flourish in the cultural sector.

This paper details the experiment’s methodology, findings, and recommendations, offering a roadmap for others seeking to implement similar approaches to responsible AI development that centre public benefit and creative communities’ interests. We hope that our work can serve as a practical model for more participatory approaches to AI dataset governance. As AI systems increasingly impact creative communities and cultural production, the frameworks and lessons developed through this work offer valuable guidance for policymakers, cultural institutions, and practitioners working to ensure AI development better serves public interests. The success of this approach demonstrates that alternative models for AI development are not only possible but practical, though they will require further interest and investment in new institutional roles and practices.

Introduction

Visions for public interest AI have been articulated, as a way to cultivate spaces that “promote[s] public goods, public orientation, and public use throughout every step of AI development and deployment.”¹ Such visions can “entitle a plurality of voices to steer AI not simply as a new category of tech products, but as a public resource and infrastructure”.² This paper presents findings from an experiment to design and operationalise new protocols for the public interest AI ecosystem through the process of running the **Choral Data ‘Trust’ Experiment**, a data governance and AI development project hosted by Serpentine, a UK public art institution.³

15 UK choirs were invited by artists Holly Herndon and Mat Dryhurst in collaboration with Serpentine to record performances of a songbook composed by the artists. The compositions and recordings of the choir performances were optimised for the collection of a choral AI dataset, purpose-built for training choral AI models for the artists’ exhibition, *The Call* **7**, presented at Serpentine between October 2024 and February 2025. The key objective of the **Choral Data ‘Trust’ Experiment**, the first of its kind at a GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums) institution, was to develop an operational framework, co-created with the choirs for the governance of the choral AI dataset for AI development as part of *The Call* and beyond.

The experiment revealed the critical importance of creating and formalising roles for trustworthy individuals and organisations in the data ecosystem, particularly in supporting foundational activities that are often overlooked in AI development and that address unbalanced or unfair dynamics in current practices of AI, such as co-production and stewardship of datasets. Furthermore, key insights emerged around the following areas:

1. **Collective Data Governance:** the experiment led to the operationalisation of new mechanisms for data stewardship extending beyond opt-in and opt-out from AI datasets.
2. **Legal Rights Collectivisation:** innovative approaches to legal frameworks are required to protect, manage and strengthen the intellectual property rights of data creators.
3. **GLAM Institutions as Data Intermediaries:** the experiment demonstrated cultural institutions’ potential to act as trusted intermediaries in public interest AI development, balancing stakeholder interests across the data and model development ecosystem.

1 Public AI **7**, Mozilla 2024.

2 Art x Public AI **7**, Future Art Ecosystems Volume 4.

3 The project’s name was inspired by Sylvie Delacroix’s and Neil D. Lawrence’s ‘Bottom-up data Trusts: disturbing the ‘one size fits all’ approach to data governance’ paper. While we initially hypothesised that a legal trust structure would be the right fit for this project, our findings led us to select a different legal mechanism. To reflect this evolution in the experiment, we use quotation marks around the word ‘trust’.

At the time of writing (February 2025), the UK is in the midst of a government consultation on AI and copyright, with parallel efforts in the EU to develop a Code of Conduct that will clarify and operationalise the EU AI Act, set to come into action later this summer. This evolving regulatory landscape presents an opportunity to move towards incentivising practices in the AI ecosystem that serve broader public interests. This paper aims to contribute towards the formation of such practices at policy and organisational levels.

O. Motivation: Expanding Participatory Approaches to AI Data Governance

The rapid advancement of AI has intensified debates around data governance, particularly around who controls and benefits from data used to develop AI systems. Independent research organisations including the Open Data Institute (ODI), Ada Lovelace Institute, Aapti Institute, Mozilla Foundation, and the Open Future Foundation have contributed important perspectives on how to ensure more equitable and participatory approaches to data governance through the practice of data stewardship. These practices have emerged in response to the widespread harms that have arisen through the current data economy, such as privacy infringements on personal data, the spread of misinformation and bias on online platforms, and the scraping of online content, including copyrighted works, for AI training datasets.

While definitions of data stewardship show slight variations in emphasis, from ODI's focus on responsible data stewardship as "*an iterative, systemic process of ensuring that data is collected, used and shared for public benefit*" ↗ to Ada Lovelace's emphasis on "*rights-preserving and participatory*" approaches ↗, they converge around core principles: responsible management of data resources, protection of individual and collective rights, and formal recognition of public value with mechanisms to ensure it is realised and fairly distributed across the entire life cycle of data.

The ODI has also developed the concept of "data institutions" ↗ – organisations that steward data on behalf of others toward public, educational or charitable aims. These institutions play vital roles in protecting sensitive data, combining data from multiple sources, creating open datasets, and enabling communities to take active roles in data governance. A related concept to data institutions are data intermediaries ↗ – organisations that facilitate data sharing between multiple stakeholders while protecting rights and interests, with seven different forms articulated in a UK Centre for Data Ethics and Innovation report ↗, including "data trusts; data exchanges; personal information management systems (PIMS); industrial data platforms; data custodians; data cooperatives; and trusted third parties."

The EU's Data Governance Act ⁷ formally recognises data intermediaries as crucial infrastructure for the digital economy, requiring them to function as neutral third parties that facilitate data sharing while being structurally separated from any other services they provide to maintain independence and avoid conflicts of interest. However, this regulatory approach focused on neutrality does not address the fundamental power asymmetry between data subjects and those developing AI models. The Ada Lovelace Institute's analysis ⁷ delves further into the operationalisation of legal mechanisms that could help address these imbalances:

1. **Data trusts:** Legal structures where trustees manage data or data rights on behalf of beneficiaries
2. **Data cooperatives:** Member-owned entities that collectively govern data resources
3. **Corporate/contractual models:** Frameworks enabling controlled data sharing between organisations

Experimentation with these models is already underway in various sectors. In healthcare, initiatives like UK Biobank ⁷ demonstrate how sensitive personal data can be stewarded for research while maintaining public trust. The humanitarian sector has seen the emergence of data collaboratives like the Humanitarian Data Exchange ⁷ to enable data sharing for social benefit. Indigenous data sovereignty movements have established new paradigms for community control over cultural heritage data, such as the Te Mana Raraunga Charter ⁷ for Māori Data Sovereignty. Other community-driven governance models have been established, such as the Posmo (Positive Mobility) data cooperative for sustainable mobility, where proceeds from the data are returned back to its members.

Within the field of AI, new models of community-led data collection and governance have been explored through data donation initiatives like Mozilla's Common Voice ⁷ and Cohere for AI's Aya Initiative ⁷. There has also been experimentation on new governance models in open source AI collaborations such as the BigScience BLOOM LLM and BigCode StarCoder LLM, through mechanisms such as ethical charters and new licenses.⁴ However, at present, participatory data governance activities are not considered for the majority of AI initiatives. As a result, data contributors often remain an unrepresented and disempowered group in the AI pipeline. This problem compounds at the intersection of arts and AI, as the work of artists and creators have been used to build generative AI models that reproduce their work often without their knowledge or benefit, without paths for recourse for consent, credit and compensation ⁷.

Building upon these prior efforts in the arts & humanities, science and AI fields, we observe that the GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums) sector offers a unique space to explore and further extend these data governance models in real world application. While traditionally not seen as active players in the development of digital technology ecosystems, GLAM institutions are holders of and stewards for multifarious cultural data with critical societal significance. To challenge this conception and explore new opportunities, the aim of the **Choral Data 'Trust' Experiment** was to test concrete pathways for responsible data intermediation by the GLAM sector in the context of AI development.

⁴ As part of the BigScience Workshop ⁷ spearheaded by Hugging Face, several data governance mechanisms were explored with the volunteer researchers who joined the initiative. This included the BigScience ethical charter ⁷, the use of an Open-RAIL license ⁷ from Responsible AI licenses, following collaborations with several libraries and archives

for data acquisition. These efforts also led to the BigCode Project ⁷, which extended the data governance efforts by creating protocols for utilising only permissively licensed data (proxy for "opt-in") and "Am I in The Stack?" ⁷ tool to enable further "opt-out."

1. Background: What role can GLAM institutions play in the AI Ecosystem?

1.1 GLAMs and Data After Generative AI

As the prevailing stewards of historical and cultural artifacts, GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums) institutions “are expected to assume a central role in society, promote participation and inclusion, [following] digitisation trends and ‘[justifying]’ their public character through wide access and representation across diverse audiences” ⁷. Historically, European GLAMs have prioritised digitisation and public domain access in order to expand access to the culture and knowledge they steward. In 2010, Europeana Foundation, a body set up by the European Commission, published a charter for policy makers, funders and GLAMs, with the core message that “the public domain should not be limited by technological protection measures or industrial property rights” ⁷. This was further augmented by the release of OpenGLAM Principles ⁷ in 2011 by Open Knowledge Foundation, and in 2020-21 Creative Commons’ Declaration on Open Access for Cultural Heritage ⁷.

However, following the rise of generative AI, principles of openness and the associated practices of permissive licensing have encountered a strategic double-bind within the OpenGLAM movement, as well as other value-aligned movements such as open science, open data and Open Source Software.⁵ On the one hand, the capabilities of such models create new methods for access to and use of knowledge, exponentially augmenting the value that open licences and public domain more generally created in terms of allowing for auditability and access to innovation to all sectors of society. On the other hand, with the concentration of the AI model training market within a few US technology companies that have enough resources to access and process large quantities of data, the training on public domain data (as well as data protected by copyright) underwrite a value transfer that further consolidates the power of the strongest players.⁶

⁵ Open Science refers to practices that make scientific research, data, and dissemination accessible to all levels of society. It encompasses transparent and collaborative processes, including open access publishing, open data sharing, and open source software development. Open Data describes data that can be freely used, reused, and redistributed by anyone, subject only to requirements to attribute and share-alike. Open Source Software (OSS) refers to software whose source code is publicly available for use, modification, and distribution under licenses that maintain openness. These three concepts are foundational to modern collaborative research and development practices, supporting reproducibility, innovation, and democratic access to knowledge. See “UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science” ⁷; European Commission’s “Open Science” policy ⁷; Open Knowledge Foundation’s “The Open Definition 2.1.” ⁷; Open Source Initiative’s “The Open Source Definition” ⁷.

⁶ See for example, Open (For Business): Big Tech, Concentrated Power, and the Political Economy of Open AI ⁷. Along similar lines, the European Parliament leveraged Anthropic’s Claude to develop Archibot ⁷, an AI system trained on the archives of the EU Parliament designed to offer better access to its documents to general users.

Among GLAM institutions, collections held by natural history museums are different from 17th century Flemish art, and these are also different to library catalogues and archival metadata on a specific period in an institution's history. All of this data may seem worlds away from genomic data sequenced from plant and animal DNA, multivariate climate data across decades of sensor readings, or terabytes of Internet data from websites like Wikipedia or Reddit. However, within the context of training generative AI models, these all fall under the category of viable and valuable 'training data'. This predicament calls both for a new strategic vision for how societal knowledge – in the form of data – is managed legally and fairly, as well as practical, context-specific implementations that make sense for different domains.

1.2 Serpentine and the Initiation of the Choral Data 'Trust' Experiment

Simultaneously, recent legal challenges⁷ and open letters⁸ from creators reflect growing concerns about AI systems being trained on creative works without meaningful consent or compensation, threatening both livelihoods and how we value human creativity. The path forward requires finding symbiotic models that can harness AI's potential while protecting and rewarding human creative labour. As a public gallery and cultural institution with a mission to create new connections between artists and society, Serpentine is actively grappling with these challenges both in terms of its internal organisational strategy and its leadership role in the broader cultural sector.

In the course of working with contemporary artists on the production and exhibition of art projects ↗, Serpentine frequently generates a variety of data related to the final artworks and exhibitions. The data can also relate to the participatory elements of art productions (e.g. in community-based projects), newly generated research materials, and audience-facing or -related data. Thus, Serpentine, like many other GLAM institutions, often acts as the producer, keeper and online distributor of data related to the gallery's activities and network.

When producing *The Call* exhibition, which features AI models that generate choral music, the artists and the Serpentine team⁹ wanted to approach the creation, use, and management of the choral AI dataset with intentionality. In parallel to the art production, Serpentine elevated the data governance aspect of the project, formalising the initiative as the **Choral Data 'Trust' Experiment** in hope that it may provide a valuable example for how GLAM organisations and other institutions stewarding data can approach governance of their datasets in the age of AI in alignment with their organisational missions.

⁷ Notable cases include: Getty Images v. Stability AI (filed January 2023 alleging copyright infringement of Getty's images for training Stable Diffusion); Sarah Silverman et al. v. Meta and OpenAI (filed July 2023 regarding unauthorized use of books for training); and Thomson Reuters v. Ross Intelligence (ongoing case about AI training on legal documents).

⁸ Open letters include: The Writers Guild of America open letter on AI use in film/TV (March 2023); "An Open Letter to Leaders in AI and Technology" signed by over 1000 AI researchers and tech leaders calling for a pause on AI development (March 2023); and The Authors Guild open letter signed by over 10,000 authors including Margaret Atwood and James Patterson protesting AI use of copyrighted works (September 2023).

⁹ Tamar Clarke-Brown (Curator); Tommie Introna (Producer); Victoria Ivanova (R&D Strategic Lead); Eva Jäger (Curator & Creative AI Lead); Vi Trinh (Assistant Curator); Ruth Waters (Producer); Kay Watson (Head of Arts Technologies).

2. Case Study: The Choral Data

‘Trust’ Experiment

2.1 The choral AI dataset

15 choirs from communities across the UK were invited to record performances of a songbook composed by artists Holly Herndon and Mat Dryhurst. The compositions and recording methods were optimised for the collection of a choral AI dataset, purpose-built for training choral AI models. Herndon and Dryhurst worked alongside researchers from IRCAM [↗](#), a French music research institute, and engineers at Stability AI to train state-of-the-art models for the exhibition *The Call* [↗](#), which was open at Serpentine from October 2024 to February 2025. This model building process is inspired by previous work by Herndon and Dryhurst on *Holly+* [↗](#), a voice AI model trained using recordings of Herndon’s own voice.

Figure 1: Snapshots from the songbook used for recording the choral AI dataset. © Leon Chew, *The Call*, Holly Herndon and Mat Dryhurst with sub, Serpentine, 2024

To collect the choral AI dataset, the Serpentine team and the artists traveled to each choir for the recording session. The resulting choral AI dataset contains 483 high-quality recordings capturing performances of vocal exercises and compositions performed by 15 UK choirs. Each recording was made using an identical technical setup: a multi-microphone array that included eight close-range microphones for soloists, four room microphones, and a first-order ambisonic microphone to capture spatial audio. The dataset includes multiple audio formats for each performance: isolated recordings from individual microphones, stereo mixes from different microphone combinations, and a main mix blending all sources. In total, over 300 choristers contributed to the dataset, including 120 featured soloists. The number of participants in the recording session differed from choir to choir, though there were typically around 12-20 choristers. However, a few of the larger sessions featured 50 or more choristers. More information about the choral AI dataset can be found in the Data Card [↗](#) on Hugging Face.

Figures 2 and 3: Image of HIVE Choir during recording of the choral AI dataset, with a multi-microphone array capturing 8 close-range microphones for soloists, 4 room microphones and a first-order ambisonic microphone. Below: Schematic of recording setup used for each recording session.

The UK choirs who contributed to the choral AI dataset are:

Blackburn People's Choir, Blackburn
Carnoustie Choir, Carnoustie
Cunninghame Choir, Beith
The Fitzhardinge Consort, Bristol
The Fourth Choir, London
HIVE Choir, Belfast
Leeds Vocal Movement, Leeds
London Contemporary Voices, London
Musarc, London
New London Chamber Choir, London
Open Arts Community Choir, Belfast
Ordsall Acappella Singers, Salford
The Ravenswood Singers, Newcastle
South Lakes A Cappella, Windermere
Spectrum Singers, Penarth

The **Choral Data 'Trust' Experiment** focused on UK choirs with primarily amateur musicians or professionals with limited platforms. Like other creative communities, many choirs currently lack access to the legal, technical and governance resources needed to shape how their creative work is used in AI training datasets. While some organisations, such as Spawning AI ↗, are developing technical tools that allow visual artists to opt out of AI model training through an online application or browser extension, there are few established pathways for different types of creative communities to proactively define and exercise control over if and how their work can be used in AI development. This is particularly true for performing artists like choirs, whose creative output may be captured and circulated online in various forms.

2.2 Legal Considerations

For different forms of data used in training AI models, particularly those produced by creatives, it is not immediately clear which areas of the law can be leveraged to challenge current AI development practices and to increase creative communities' agency. While individual legal rights might be limited in the context of AI development, identification of available legal mechanisms nonetheless constitutes an important starting point for better understanding the scope of action and strategies that are possible within a given scenario.

For the choral AI dataset, produced by creatives in the UK, we focus on UK performers' rights and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹⁰ rights to explore opportunities for the choristers to exercise their rights as one collective voice, with more discussion in 2.4 below on our findings of the limits and opportunities when configuring these rights into a trusted data intermediary framework.

Performers' Rights¹¹

Under UK law (specifically Part II of the Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1988), performers automatically receive certain intellectual property (IP) rights when their performances are recorded. These performers' rights include:

- The right to consent to or prohibit the recording of a live performance
- The right to control how recordings of their performance are used, copied, or distributed
- The right to equitable remuneration when recordings are played in public or communicated to the public
- Moral rights, including the right to be identified as the performer
- The right to object to derogatory treatment of their performance

These rights include both economic rights - relating to the creation and use of recordings - and moral rights, such as the right to be identified as the performer.

Rather than having performers assign away their rights (a common industry practice, although performers can also get remunerated through copyright societies like PRS for Music), we developed an alternative approach: performers licensed their IP rights to a trusted intermediary who could then manage downstream uses of the recordings in both the dataset and AI model training. While there is ongoing legal debate about whether AI training constitutes copying of protected material, we established a standardised licensing framework between choir members and the intermediary, including templates for sub-licensing to potential AI developers.

¹⁰ The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is the European Union's comprehensive data protection and privacy regulation that came into force in 2018. It gives individuals rights over their personal data and places obligations on organizations that collect and process such data. The UK adopted the same regulation into national law as the UK GDPR after exiting the European Union, maintaining alignment with EU data protection standards.

¹¹ The information provided in this section reflects the legal advice provided by Alasdair Taylor of Keystone Law, and does not constitute general advice.

This model offers a practical pathway that balances two key interests: it allows performers to maintain control over their economic and moral rights while giving AI developers clear terms for responsible innovation with high-quality training data. The approach reduces legal uncertainty for all parties while preserving performers' agency over how their creative work is used.

Data Rights¹²

GDPR rights arise in circumstances where processing – even if this only amounts to storage – of personal data is taking place.¹³ Under GDPR, such processing requires a lawful basis. In this project, the joint controllers (Serpentine Arts Technologies, Holly Herndon and Mat Dryhurst, and IRCAM) relied on Article 6(1)(f) UK GDPR (legitimate interests) as the legal basis for data processing at different stages. While processing under legitimate interests does not require explicit consent from data subjects, it does require transparency about data use and provides data subjects with several key rights:

- Right to be informed about the processing of their personal data
- Right to access their personal data
- Right to object to processing under certain circumstances
- Right to request erasure of their personal data (with specific conditions)
- Right to request rectification of inaccurate personal data

The table below outlines three key stages of data processing in the choral recording project and where GDPR rights apply:

1. **Recording Stage:** When recording the choirs, all singers were considered data subjects since they were identifiable. While singers technically had rights to erasure and objection, in practice these couldn't be exercised after the fact since recording was a one-time event. Singers could only opt-out beforehand.
2. **Storage and Cleaning Stage:** Only solo singers remained identifiable since their tracks were individually labelled. Group recordings were not considered personal data since individual voices were blended together. Solo singers had rights to transparency, objection, erasure, and access to their recordings.
3. **AI Model Training Stage:** Similar to the storage stage, only solo singers maintained GDPR rights. While they could exercise rights like objection and erasure for future uses, they couldn't "unwind" the training of AI models once completed. Transparency and access rights remained.

¹² The information provided in this section reflects the legal advice provided to the project by Alex Lawrence-Archer of AWO, and does not constitute legal advice on which any other person should rely.

¹³ Personal data is defined in UK GDPR as any information relating to an identified or identifiable living individual ('data subject'). An identifiable individual is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, identification number, location data, online identifier or to one or more factors specific to their physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity.

	<p>1. Recording Choirs: Serpentine Arts Technologies (SAT), and Holly Herndon and Mat Dryhurst (Artists), carrying out recording sessions with the UK choirs, using music written by Holly Herndon and Mat Dryhurst. At each recording, multiple tracks are recorded, including (i) recordings of the choir ensemble, and (ii) individually labelled tracks for solo singers in each choir (the ‘Solo Singers’)</p>
<p>(Joint) Data Controller(s)</p>	<p>SAT and Artists have worked closely together to design the project and the approach to the recordings. They are joint controllers for this processing.</p>
<p>When</p>	<p>June - July 2024</p>
<p>Processing of personal data?</p>	<p>Yes: making the recordings is an act of processing and all singers are identifiable to the controllers. The purpose of processing is to facilitate the overall project (i.e. to run the exhibition and create the AI models for exploitation).</p>
<p>Data subjects</p>	<p>All singers</p>
<p>Legal Basis</p>	<p>Article 6(1)(f) Legitimate interest. Data subjects were informed through a Privacy Notice.</p>
<p>Relevant UK GDPR rights¹⁴</p>	<p>In theory, data subjects have the right to erasure and to object. However, this stage only covers the <i>making</i> of the recordings (as distinct from their storage or use).</p> <p>In practice therefore, the data subjects for this stage of processing cannot object to it or seek erasure, since the processing is a one-off event. They can, however, opt-out.</p>

¹⁴ We cover only data rights which are *relevant* in the sense of having a role in empowering data subjects or constraining the actions of data controllers.

2. Storage and cleaning of data: In the first instance, SAT stored the recordings and cleaned the data.	
(Joint) Data Controller(s)	SAT. NB: IRCAM and any freelancers engaged by the Artists but contracted by SAT are likely processors rather than controllers, since they are not determining why and how to exploit the recordings, merely assisting in that process.
When	July - August 2024
Processing of personal data?	Yes , in respect of the recordings of the Solo Singers, since these are individually labelled and hence identifiable. Exploitation of Solo Singers' recordings permits them to be identified. No , in respect of the group recordings. The nature of these recordings and the blending of voices means that no one individual can be identified from them (and therefore from exploitation of them).
Data subjects	Solo Singers only.
Legal Basis	Article 6(1)(f) Legitimate interest. Solo Singers Data subjects were informed through a Privacy Notice.
Relevant UK GDPR rights	Transparency: Participants expressed a wish to be kept informed about how the raw recordings were being stored, shared and exploited. The Solo Singers are entitled to this transparency from SAT, Artists, IRCAM and any other parties using the recordings. Objection and Erasure: Exploitation of the raw recordings which has not been agreed at the outset of the project is said to be prohibited or to require agreement. Whilst data rights cannot reflect this precisely, the Solo Singers could object to any future processing exploitation or seek erasure of the recordings. This gives the Solo Singers a degree of control/bargaining power over future exploitation of the raw recordings, provided they are kept aware of SAT's and others' plans for them. Access: The Solo Singers would be entitled to receive copies of the recordings of <i>their respective voices</i> ¹⁵ from SAT.

¹⁵ But **not** of the overall choir.

3. Training of AI Models: SAT, IRCAM and Artists used raw and processed data for the purposes of training various AI models. ¹⁶	
(Joint) Data Controller(s)	SAT, Artists and IRCAM.
When	July - August 2024
Processing of personal data?	<p>Yes, in respect of the recordings of the Solo Singers, since these are individually labelled and hence identifiable. Exploitation of Solo Singers’ recordings permits them to be identified.</p> <p>No, in respect of the group recordings. The nature of these recordings and the blending of voices means that no one individual can be identified from them (and therefore from exploitation of them).</p>
Data subjects	Solo Singers only.
Legal Basis	Article 6(1)(f) Legitimate interest. Solo Singers Data subjects were informed through a Privacy Notice.
Relevant UK GDPR rights ¹⁷	<p>Transparency: Participants expressed a wish to be kept informed about how the raw recordings were being stored, shared and exploited. The Solo Singers are entitled to this transparency from SAT, Artists, IRCAM and any other parties using the recordings.</p> <p>Objection and Erasure: Exploitation of the raw recordings which has not been agreed at the outset of the Project is said to be prohibited or to require agreement. Whilst data rights cannot reflect this precisely, the Solo Singers could object to any future processing exploitation or seek erasure of the recordings. This gives the Solo Singers a degree of control/bargaining power over future exploitation of the raw recordings, provided they are kept aware of SAT’s and others’ plans for them.</p> <p><i>Note key limitations here, however. Solo Singers will have bargaining power where they can exercise these rights prospectively, which assumes they are informed in advance. Some uses of the raw recordings – notably the training of new AI models – cannot be ‘unwound’ using these rights, since no UK GDPR rights subsist in the trained AI model.</i></p> <p>Access: The Solo Singers would be entitled to receive copies of the recordings of <i>their respective voices</i>¹⁸ from SAT.</p>

¹⁶ As the situation is unclear, we assume that the training of the Artists Model, though it is further removed from the recordings, involves some use of the raw voice recordings.

¹⁷ We cover only data rights which are *relevant* in the sense of having a role in empowering data subjects or constraining the actions of data controllers in a way which touches on the ‘Uses and Permissions’ explainer provided by Serpentine Arts Technologies.

¹⁸ But **not** of the overall choir.

The use of trained models and their outputs did not constitute personal data processing, as the AI models developed in *The Call* generate synthetic voices that are amalgamations rather than replications of individual voices. While it is technically possible to develop models that do replicate identifiable voices, as demonstrated by various voice cloning technologies, such models would fall under GDPR regulation and grant rights to the individuals whose voices are replicated. However, for the current project, desired constraints on model use and output (like profit sharing arrangements) must be established through other legal frameworks since data protection law does not apply. This represents a significant limitation of current GDPR legislation in addressing AI-generated audio content, though the situation differs for other AI models that do enable individual identification, such as text generators that can output people's names and personal information.

The distinction created by the GDPR between the choristers who were part of the chorus and those who were solo singers in terms of drawing a boundary between those who are data subject and who are not further emphasises the need for additional participatory and governance mechanisms that allow all choristers to come together as a group. For example, many participants expressed a wish to be kept informed about how the recordings were being stored, shared and exploited, however only the solo singers are legally entitled to this transparency from the joint controllers or any other party using the recordings. Could the rights of the few be leveraged in order to bargain for general terms that the law is unable to grant to all choir members? What type of organisational vehicle would be required to increase the bargaining power of the choristers as a creative community?

It is critical to underline that such questions go beyond the necessary legal requirements, yet they are central to developing appropriate mechanisms to balance the relationship between contributors to/stakeholders in datasets and AI developers. While legislation such as the GDPR provides important baseline protections for personal data, it is insufficient alone to address the governance challenges posed by AI training data since the value of data is cumulative and relational.¹⁹ The GDPR's technologically neutral approach and focus on individual rights creates gaps when dealing with collective data resources and fails to address power imbalances between data subjects and the organisations collecting and processing data at scale.²⁰ The framework's emphasis on individual consent and control is particularly ill-suited for managing institutional collections and cultural heritage data being used as AI training data, where the "data subjects" may be diffuse or historical, and where collective interests in preservation and access need to be balanced against commercial exploitation.

¹⁹ See Salome Viljoen 'A relational theory for data governance,' Yale Law Journal, 131(2), 573–645 ↗.

²⁰ See Janis Wong's 'Co-creating Data Protection Solutions Through a Commons' ↗.

2.3 Building Capacity for Collective Data Governance

Alongside the challenges of exploring the current rights landscape for data contributors, the **Choral Data ‘Trust’ Experiment** also presented the challenge of scaling up data governance with over 300 choristers with different backgrounds, sentiments towards generative AI and preferences for governance practices.

Technical approaches to data governance are emerging, such as tools that provide data subjects transparency into whether their data is present in AI training datasets [↗](#) or preference signalling [↗](#) for data creators for how their data is used for AI training. However, governance solutions that focus solely on individual opt-in or opt-out put the burden on individual creators to act and limit engagement possibilities to simply providing or withdrawing consent, with few affordances to shape the overall AI building process and outcomes. There are also open questions for how to provide other foundational components of data governance, such as building trust with and accounting for diverse preferences for datasets with many contributors.²¹ These are often not achievable through exclusively technical and automated methods.

Thus, one of the first steps in the **Choral Data ‘Trust’ Experiment** was the hiring of an independent data steward (Jennifer Ding), in order to adapt and integrate data stewardship practices to the project-specific context. Because the project was set up to explore community-driven data governance, instead of prescribing an established governance method and vehicle, the data steward focused on enabling organic emergence of governance practices and priorities through engagement with the choirs. Therefore, the data steward’s primary role was to surface, synthesise and translate preferences from across the choirs and choristers into forms that could be used to directly shape technical practices and legal documents.

In order to enable joint governance of the choral AI dataset by large groups of data subjects, the data steward built up capacity for collective governance through the following activities:

- **Activity 1:** Building relationships: organising conversations with choir representatives over email or video calls to get to know each choir and create opportunities for targeted questions and discussion (Section 2.3.1 [↗](#))
- **Activity 2:** Building understanding: hosting online Choral Data Conversations and Data Governance meetings open to every choir member who was part of the project to share information and discuss the project (Section 2.3.1 [↗](#))
- **Activity 3:** Surfacing data preferences: running a Data Preferences survey which received 100+ responses to gather preferences towards how the dataset would be used and governed (Section 2.3.2 [↗](#))
- **Activity 4:** Surfacing licence preferences: running a Licence Preferences Polis which received 700+ anonymous votes to identify distinct preference groups towards potential data/model licensing terms (Section 2.3.3 [↗](#))

²¹ See for example, Public attitudes to data and AI: Tracker survey (Wave 4) report, UK Department of Science, Innovation, & Technology [↗](#), and 2024 Edelman Trust Barometer [↗](#).

Participation in all activities was voluntary and for the non-anonymous activities, we encouraged representation from each choir. For a detailed breakdown of cross-choir participation across the different activities, see B. Choir Participation in Engagement Activities ↗ in the Appendix. Findings and outcomes from the engagement were documented in a public Google Drive folder ↗ for easy access for the choir members and to enable reusability by other data governance practitioners.

In the following sections, we share findings and outcomes from these participatory activities and in Section 2.3.4 ↗ map our translation process to shape technical practices, governance interventions and legal mechanisms from the preferences shared by the choir contributors.

2.3.1 Building Relationships & Understanding

With ‘trust’ as a foundational component of the experiment, the project began with the building of relationships across different groups involved. This included the initial outreach to the choirs by Serpentine Arts Technologies’ production team, in particular Ruth Waters and Eva Jäger, as well as the in person recording sessions in each choir’s hometown with the artists. Through this process of creating and sharing art and building understanding of the project through in person conversations, this laid the foundation for further conversations about the dataset.

Once the data steward joined the team, they were introduced to each choir for a 1:1 chat with choir representatives (Activity 1: Building Relationships) to learn more about each choir’s interests and concerns and to share more about the opportunity to get involved in the governance of the jointly created dataset. The data steward then hosted three Choral Data Conversations (May 2024) and two Data Governance Meetings (August, September 2024), which together constituted Activity 2: Building Understanding. Each call took place on Zoom. The presentations, agenda and minutes from each meeting were made publicly available ↗ so that choir members who were not able to attend were able to catch up and learn more.

Each session started with a presentation about the project and key data questions, and then transitioned to an interactive discussion facilitated by Slido followed by an open conversation to close the meeting. The sessions introduced key themes for group discussion including the role of data (especially voice data) in building AI, current capabilities of voice AI, data rights for voice data subjects, the transformation of art and performance into data and decision making methods for datasets. A public template ↗ for these conversations about voice AI is available for reuse.

Through these conversations, a key early discovery was the recognition of the discomfort around using the term ‘data’ when referring to choral performance. Choristers described this as ‘dehumanising’, ‘disembodied’, ‘disempowering’ and ‘robotic’ while also ‘exciting’ and an opportunity for the project to create a ‘best in example’. Feedback following the sessions included the following quotes from participants:

- *‘Thank you for an interesting and informative session, raising questions I’ve never really considered before... we hadn’t really understood the purpose [of the data governance project] until now’;*
- *‘Thank you for the time and care to do this work; it feels very new; as an artist, this kind of intentionality is really striking me; feels respectful and much needed in the time of change’;*
- *‘Love what you’re doing with prioritising respectful collaboration from the start. Informed consent mechanisms in accessible formats [very important]’;*
- *‘It was interesting also that folks in the poll were less keen in having [the data steward represent] us - I think that in an ideal world where our attention is not scattered in a thousand different directions it would be great if we could advocate for ourselves - but the reality is that we would not have even known to ask before we had this meeting...’;*
- *‘The fact that you, as an informed person, who has our best interests at heart, are paying proper attention to this is such a luxury. Isn’t it mad though, that we as a society put so little value upon ourselves and this information? I hope this is the beginning of a turn towards a better way’;*
- *‘Important for us to remember that the artists [Holly and Mat] have agency as well... I hope as a group we don’t get so excited about control that we restrict what is possible’;*
- *‘Some choirs will have that data and legal expertise in house, but not all will, so I worry that there’s the potential for there to be inequality of access to key background knowledge that will inform decision-making’.*

2.3.2 Data Preferences Survey Findings

Inspired by the initial Choral Data Conversations in May, the data steward created a 28 question survey ↗ (22 required, 6 optional), which covered topics such as background information on the respondent, sentiment towards the project, preferences for data/model building practices, credit and compensation preferences, data governance preferences, and intervention priorities in the model building pipeline. Outcomes from the surveys were published in a public report ↗ to share with the choirs, which included results as well as an FAQ section to answer some of the questions raised in responses around project-specific practices for the art production, data cleaning and data practices.

Our aim was to have at least one respondent from each of the participating choirs, and the survey received 103 responses from 14 of the 15 choirs (London Contemporary Voices joined the project after the survey was completed). While Carnoustie Choir only had one respondent, the other choirs on the lower end of participation had at least 4 respondents and on the higher end of participation, Ravenswood Singers and The Fourth Choir had 12-14 respondents. Reflecting the demographics of the UK choirs, the respondents came from wide ranging age groups from 20s to 70s and the median time respondents have been in the choir was 5 years.

An interesting finding was that the large majority of the respondents both wanted to know who has access to the recording data and also how the data is stored, accessed, and used (74.5%), but were also comfortable with the recordings being posted online (e.g. YouTube, social media) (74.5%), an action which could directly compromise the ability to track who has access to the data. This discrepancy may reflect the often disjointed motivations between technology platforms and artists (especially live performers), where the former are focused on leveraging digital traces of the art as raw material and the latter are often focused on the ephemeral process of creating or sharing the art with others. Through the process of widely sharing art on platforms like YouTube or Instagram, creators may not have fully considered the consequences of widening access to their content to a range of actors for many possible different use cases.

Concern of misalignment between data creators and data users was reflected in survey outcomes, as over 25% of participants responded that they were not comfortable with use of their data by users beyond the project to train an AI model. This stood in contrast to only 4% of participants responding that they were not comfortable with Herndon and Dryhurst creating the choral AI model for the exhibition. This indicates that transparency about data practices may mitigate unease and distrust surrounding datafication and model building processes. This also indicates that blanket opt-in and opt-out do not capture critical nuances of consent preferences, as context of use and user intentions may matter more than the act itself of sharing data for generative AI. The survey also highlights that participants were more interested in group recognition, with over 92% of participants indicating interest in choir level credit, while only 34% indicating interest in individual credit. This is further evidence that governance mechanisms should be able to interface with groups rather than solely individuals.

Figure 4: Results from the Data Preferences Survey showing change in comfort towards different users of the dataset (above) and contribution credit preferences (below)

Survey findings on data governance preferences revealed interesting insights. For decisions about data access (39.2%) and future uses of the data (34.3%), the most popular choice among the four governance options (e.g. vote by all choristers, vote by choir representative or committee of choir representatives, Serpentine team decides) was the vote by choir representatives. However, the most popular choice for decisions about data representation in the exhibit was for the Serpentine team to decide (38.2%). At the same time, over 80% of respondents shared that they were not interested in participating in governance decisions more than two times a year. This indicates that while individuals believe choir representation in governance is important, there is limited capacity for many individuals to serve as the choir representatives. A representative body of different stakeholders in the project could serve as a vehicle to enable representation in decisions while reducing the burden on individuals.

In light of these survey findings, the data steward set up the Data Governance working group which invited choir members to join in discussions around the project use and future use of the dataset during two Data Governance meetings. In response to feedback on the need for more information on the legal aspects of the project (e.g. data and IP rights), the second meeting featured a discussion with the project's legal advisors from AWO Agency and Keystone Law.

2.3.3 Licence Preferences Polis Findings

Across the choirs and individuals, there were differences in risk tolerance and openness to data sharing, important considerations for setting licence terms for the choral AI dataset and models. Informed by the Data Preference Survey findings, Data Governance meetings and guidance from legal advisors, the data steward set up another survey to further clarify group preferences around future use of the choral AI dataset to inform licensing terms and selection.

This survey was run through Pol.is , which was shared with the choirs and other project stakeholders.

37 people cast 705 votes, which resulted in 3 opinion groups: A, B and C (see: Figure 5). While Group C was more permissive in their views towards sharing and wider reuse of the choral AI dataset and models, Groups A and B were more cautious, against public sharing and commercial and profit-generating use cases. Consensus was reached for the majority of statements, which helped highlight the most divisive statements such as "I think the choral AI dataset/model should be available for commercial and profit-generating use cases." Statements with broad agreement also proved a useful directive, with 90% of voters agreeing that the choral AI dataset should be shared with users who comply with the licence terms and around 80% interested in sharing for non-commercial use cases that re-licence under the same terms and credit the choirs for their contribution. On the governance side, 75% respondents also agreed (and 3% disagreed) with the statement: *'I think access to the choral AI dataset should be gated by a trusted intermediary who can vet requests by other users'*, reflecting interest in a governance body that is responsible for managing data access requests.

% Agreed
 % Disagreed
 % Passed
 % Didn't Vote

These findings indicate that if the choral AI dataset is released, a licence like the Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commercial Share Alike (CC-BY-NC-SA) ↗ would be a good fit for the model to meet group preferences. The Pol.is findings serve as a snapshot of group preferences for licensing, but can be used as an incomplete but indicative representation of choir preferences in future negotiations with AI developers when selecting licences and release strategies for the choral AI dataset and models.

Figure 5: Pol.is statements with the highest levels of disagreement among preference groups and agreement among preference groups

2.3.4 Translating Data Contributor Preferences to Governance Mechanisms

The purpose of the choir engagement activities was to build capacity for governance among the choirs and surface preferences to guide technical practice during the project and shape legal mechanisms that can enable operationalising their preferences, via IP rights and to some extent, data rights. Following the steward's work gathering and synthesising data and licensing preferences into findings and recommendations, the team turned their attention to translating these into concrete actions and viable governance mechanisms. To visualise these priorities, the steward created a map to share with choirs on the priority interventions across the choral AI model building process (see: Figure 6) around data transparency and co-creation that were surfaced through the Data Preferences survey. This included the sharing of data privacy notices, more detailed documentation (in the Data Preferences Report FAQ [↗](#)) on data practices, and the creation of the Pol.is to set relevant terms for the license.

Figure 6: Priority interventions across the choral AI model building pipeline

However, the team recognised that to move this activity from the space of good intentions towards a governance process with legal backing, further legal design was required. With the guidance of legal advisors, the team proposed creating the following legal mechanisms:

- **Performance Rights Agreement**, buoyed by the choristers' **IP rights** to concretise the preferences choristers shared in the **Data Preferences Survey**, particularly around permissions related to downstream uses in AI development, crediting and compensation;
- **Data Rights Mandate**, for soloists whose voices, and thus Personally Identifiable Information (PII) are identifiable in the dataset, to create an intermediary that can support exercising their rights as a group, based on outcomes from the **Choral Data Conversations** for the need for support to keep up with progress in the AI field, as well as the **License Preferences Pol.is** and to support vetting data access to new users
- **Trusted Data Intermediary**, a body with representation from the choirs, artists and Serpentine that can create and formalise these agreements and serve as an ongoing decision making and stewardship body for future data governance, based on outcomes from the License Preferences Polis

For further information on the mapping of choir engagement activity and the surfaced preferences to the final legal mechanisms, as well as the purpose of each mechanism and the relevant rights under UK law, see Table 1 [↗](#).

2.4 Setting up a Trusted Data Intermediary at Serpentine

Individual data subjects often struggle to exercise their data and IP rights effectively within the AI ecosystem. Data collection, dataset creation and AI model training frequently occur without individuals' knowledge or consent, and without providing them meaningful benefits. Moreover, since data's value increases through combination and aggregation, individual-level interventions in AI development are less effective than collective approaches.

'Collectivising' rights, – for example through consumer class actions or unions, – has proven to be an effective strategy for increasing individuals' agency within legal frameworks where individual rights alone provide insufficient leverage. Additionally, aggregating rights through dedicated organisational structures can reduce the burden on individuals of monitoring, auditing and taking action regarding their data rights.

While establishing an organisational entity was a core objective of the experiment from the outset, its precise form and mandate were initially undefined. The direction for this entity emerged through iterative engagement between the data steward and the choirs, incorporating additional input from the Serpentine team, wider Serpentine management, and the artists.

Exploring Different Legal Routes for the Set Up of a Data ‘Trust’

Central to the experiment was the goal of enabling collective bargaining power and coordinated action through establishing a dedicated legal entity that could ‘own’ or control data and intellectual property rights on behalf of individual choristers. We explored several possible legal vehicles, drawing on the Ada Lovelace Institute’s report on legal mechanisms for data stewardship [↗](#) and Delacroix and Lawrence’s work on data trusts [↗](#). With support from legal counsel, we evaluated three potential structures: an individual trustee, a legal trust, and a company limited by guarantee.

Given the project’s initial framing as a data trust experiment, we first explored establishing a Data Trustee. While in England and Wales legal trusts can be relatively simple to establish, they are not a legal entity per se, but rather a relationship between stakeholders where the trustee acts as a representative legal person. Although this structure benefits from the trustee’s fiduciary duty to beneficiaries, it presents challenges when engaging with downstream dataset users, primarily due to the trustee’s exposure to unlimited personal liability. While a corporate entity could act as trustee and address the liability issue, this would require £100,000 in paid-up shares. Additional barriers included extensive HMRC compliance requirements, and uncertainty about whether GDPR rights – while delegatable for exercise – could be considered ‘property’ held in trust.

We ultimately selected Serpentine LLC, an existing trading entity that supports Serpentine’s commercial activities, to implement the company limited by guarantee structure. This decision, reached jointly by the Serpentine team and data steward, was based on several factors:

- Straightforward setup with minimal costs
- Limited liability protection
- Operational efficiency through integration with the entity that oversaw dataset production
- Deep understanding of the cultural and technological context that would inform the dataset’s potential value

Furthermore, Serpentine LLC, acting as a trusted data intermediary, enables:

1. Individual Rights Management: Soloists can mandate Serpentine LLC to exercise their GDPR rights collectively while retaining their individual right to exercise these rights independently;
2. Collective Governance: Choirs can shape how future users access and use the choral AI dataset through sub-licensing terms incorporated into the general licensing agreement between individual choristers and Serpentine LLC.

Governance Mechanism	Relevant Rights	Source Activity for Contributor Preferences	Purpose
Performance Rights Agreement	UK Performers' (IP) Rights	Data Preferences Survey	Set terms between TDI and choristers that collectivises individual performers' rights for downstream usage of the dataset, including permissible uses and types of users, as well as data security, crediting, and compensation practices
Data Rights Mandate	Data Rights, under UK GDPR	Choral Data Conversations. Licence Preferences Polis	Enable solo singers whose voices (PII) are captured in the dataset to mandate TDI to support the group by monitoring ongoing use, sharing information and exercising data rights
Trusted Data Intermediary (TDI)	UK Contract Law	Licence Preferences Polis	Formalises Serpentine LLC as legal entity for TDI for contracts (sub-licensing) and as admin hub responsible for enforcing the Performance Rights Agreement and Data Rights Mandate

Figure 6: Trusted Data Intermediary framework for the Choral Data 'Trust' Experiment
Table 1: Mapping from choir engagement activities to governance mechanisms created

3. Call to Action: Building Data Intermediaries for a Public Interest AI Ecosystem

3.1 Reflections

3.1.1 Data Steward's Reflections

'My guiding vision ↗ for stewardship of the choral AI dataset has centred on the question: how can we create AI datasets with intention, meaning with respect, recognition and responsibility to data contributors? This means treating a digital connection established through co-creating a dataset as a relationship and facing the personal, legal and artistic implications that come with. Through further investment in the human infrastructure that surrounds data governance, such as the individuals and organisations that can serve as data intermediaries, this will bring necessary flexibility to the process of data governance and a human touch to what can otherwise be a confusing and alienating process of transforming art and identity into raw material for building AI models. Technical tools can support the aggregating and actioning of group decisions, but humans in the governance loop are needed to build relationships and understanding that enable trust in and legitimacy of any governance decision.'

– Jennifer Ding

3.1.2 Serpentine's Reflections

'Serpentine's guiding vision for initiating and facilitating the Data 'Trust' Experiment was formulated in a strategic briefing published by the organisation's R&D wing, Future Art Ecosystems in March 2024, Art x Public AI ↗. At that stage, the discourse on public interest AI was still very nascent, particularly in the GLAM sector. Nevertheless, it was clear to us that the experimental end of art and technology productions could serve as a sandbox for new organisational practices and forms. We were particularly interested in 'speedrunning and developing early operational frameworks for data stewardship, data bargaining, data valuation, and stakeholder coordination of data' ↗, which a collaboration with artists Holly Herndon and Mat Dryhurst for their Serpentine commission enabled us to do. While the trusted data intermediary framework that emerged was particular to the facts of this specific AI project, we believe that it offers a primitive for application specific AI model development that relies on high quality data, which will often require the production of curated datasets. However, as the extensive investment in data stewardship and legal support has shown, this is not a capability that organisations, particularly public GLAM organisations can achieve without considerable financial, technical and training support.'

– Victoria Ivanova

3.2 Recommendations

The **Choral Data ‘Trust’ Experiment** revealed insights in three key areas, all of which would benefit from further research, experimentation and support:

1. Collective Data Governance

The experiment demonstrated that meaningful participation in AI development requires approaches beyond individual opt-in/opt-out. To enable data contributors like creatives to have a genuine voice in the process, two elements are essential:

- Enhanced public digital literacy, particularly regarding AI systems and what constitutes acceptable use of data
- Further investment in data stewardship experiments and infrastructure to address challenges that arise from in practice and real world contexts

2. Legal Rights Collectivisation

The effectiveness of innovative legal frameworks depends on their enforceability. Several key areas need attention:

- Clarification of data rights mandates under GDPR
- Clear guidance on IP rights in AI model development and downstream uses
- New legislative approaches to protect public interests in AI systems, given the limitations of individual rights and without additional undue burden to individuals
- Improved access to legal support as an enabler of collective data governance rather than just a tool for contestation

3. GLAM Institutions as Trusted Intermediaries

The experiment highlighted GLAM institutions’ potential to balance stakeholder interests across the AI development ecosystem. This suggests the need for:

- An industrial policy for the creative sector that supports further experimentation
- Development of cultural heritage and artistic data policies
- Enhanced capacity for cultural institutions to meaningfully engage with AI technologies
- We hope to collaborate with more organisations in the future to further clarify, standardise and advance both the theoretical foundations and operational praxis of trusted data intermediaries, so that this kind of data institution can be more configurable and usable by more organisations in service of building towards a flourishing public AI ecosystem.

Appendix

A. Glossary of Key Terms

- **Artists:** Holly Herndon and Mat Dryhurst
- **Choral AI dataset:** choir performance recording data, recording data, performance data, of which Data Subjects will have access to or governance over
- **Choral AI model:** model trained using the dataset by the Artists or other Data Users
- **Data Contributors/Creators:** Choirs and their members who agreed to participate in The Call, exhibition project by artists Holly Herndon and Mat Dryhurst, in the context of which choral AI models were developed using the choral recordings for training
- **Data Intermediary:** individual or organisation that facilitates engagement, negotiation, and decision making amongst the data stakeholders in the data ecosystem
- **Data User(s):** the individuals or organisations who have the ability to access and repurpose the recorded data under the data sub-licensing terms
- **Serpentine Trust:** the gallery and the team who convene and organise the project
- **Serpentine Arts Technologies (SAT):** A department at a public art institution, Serpentine, located in London, UK. SAT is focused on supporting artists who work with advanced technologies, as well as on developing an art and advanced technologies ecosystem for the public good through its R&D programme, Future Art Ecosystems.
- **Trusted Data Intermediary (TDI):** a data intermediary whose role has been established through good faith legal and governance processes

B. Choir Participation in Engagement Activities

The following tables describe engagement from each choir for different activities. Because the Licence Preferences Polis was fully anonymous, no choir affiliation information was collected. For the online calls from Activity 1 and 2, there was at least one representative from each choir who attended one of the five calls. For the Data Preferences survey in Activity 3, there was representation from 14 out of the 15 choirs. The only choir (London Contemporary Voices) not represented in the survey joined the project after the survey had been released.

Table A.1:
Number of attendees from each choir across the 5 online calls

Number of Attendees	Choirs
0-1 Participants	Cunninghame Choir South Lakes Acapella Ordsall Acappella Singers Ravenswood Singers Blackburn Peoples Choir London Contemporary Voices
2-3 Participants	New London Chamber Choir Spectrum Singers Carnoustie Choir Leeds Vocal Movement Fourth Choir Fitzhardinge Consort
4-10 Participants	HIVE Choir Musarc Open Arts Community Choir

**Table A.2:
Responses and representation rate across choirs in the Data Preference Survey**

Response Rates	Choirs, by Percentage of Representation
1-5 Responses	Carnoustie Choir (1%) Blackburn People's Choir (3.9%) HIVE Choir (3.9%) Ordsall Acappella Singers (3.9%) Cunninghame Choir (4.9%)
6-10 Response	New London Chamber Choir (5.8%) South Lakes Acapella (6.8%) Spectrum Singers (6.8%) Fitzhardinge Consort (7.8%) Leeds Vocal Movement (9.7%) Open Arts Community Choir (9.7%)
11-15 Responses	Musarc (10.7%) Ravenswood Singers (11.7%) The Fourth Choir (13.6%)

About Future Art Ecosystems

Future Art Ecosystems (FAE) is a project for building 21st century cultural infrastructure to support art and advanced technologies for the public good.

Serpentine established the Arts Technologies department in 2014 to lead on commissioning and production of artworks that engage with advanced technologies. What followed was an exciting series of collaborations with artists James Bridle, Ian Cheng, Jenna Sutela, Hito Steyerl and Jakob Kudsk Steensen leading to the development of new experimental artworks that deployed a variety of technologies from AI to VR and game engines. Each piece relied on the development of bespoke hybrid teams, technological systems and legal agreements – all of which offered unique insights into these technologies, and equally made evident the operational limitations of undertaking this type of cultural production in the context of a ‘legacy’ art institution.

It was the coupling of the opportunity to shine light on the R&D potential of artistic production processes, and the challenge of imagining new infrastructures to better support the evolving art and advanced technologies ecosystem, that led to the emergence of Future Art Ecosystems. In close collaboration with Rival Strategy, we (the Arts Technologies team) launched the annual FAE strategic briefings with our first publication, Future Art Ecosystems 1: Art x Advanced Technologies in 2020. Rooted in conversations with a diverse network of participants, the briefings have become widely shared resources that inform the practices and long-term strategies of artists, institutions and the wider cultural ecosystem, highlighting the role of FAE as an ecosystem-oriented project.

Today, FAE builds on the insights gained through the strategic briefings to develop partnerships and facilitate projects that are focused on what we consider to be the key priority areas for art x advanced technologies infrastructural development. Together with a wide range of collaborators – ranging from cultural institutions, artists, producers, curators, researchers and technologists to businesses, policy makers and mission-oriented organisations – we’re committed to researching, prototyping and building 21st century cultural infrastructure to support art and advanced technologies for the public good.

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